

Co-Designing AI-Enhanced E-Participation. Insights from ORBIS Participatory Approaches to Democratic Deliberation

Ilaria Mariani, Francesca Rizzo

Department of Design, Politecnico di Milano, 20158, Milano, Italy
ilaria1.mariani@polimi.it; francesca.rizzo@polimi.it

Abstract. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly embedded in civic technologies, including e-participation tools and platforms designed to support democratic deliberation. Yet, while a growing “participatory turn” in AI design (Delgado et al., 2023) promotes stakeholder engagement, participation is often enacted as a discrete format or early-stage aspiration rather than as a sustained process embedded across the lifecycle of AI systems. This paper examines how Participatory Design (PD) operates as a socio-technical mediation mechanism in the development of AI-enhanced e-participation tools and platforms. Drawing on the Horizon Europe project ORBIS and its six deliberative pilots, the study builds on Delgado et al.’s (2023) four analytical dimensions—goals, scope, participants, and methods—to elaborate an intermediate theoretical account of how PD structures negotiation between differentiated deliberative practices and AI configurations over time. The findings show that AI-enhanced deliberation becomes democratically meaningful not through technological optimisation alone, but through sustained mediation that aligns civic practices with evolving technological affordances under institutional constraints and deliberative needs. The paper contributes a structured account of PD as a longitudinal socio-technical mediation process for developing AI-enhanced civic technologies beyond isolated engagement interventions.

Keywords: AI, E-participation, Co-design, Deliberative Democracy, AI-enhanced deliberation.

1 Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly embedded in digital systems designed to mediate interaction between citizens and public institutions. These systems—often referred to as civic technologies—include e-participation platforms and tools that support public consultation, deliberation, participatory budgeting, and policy dialogue [1, 2]. Within this broader category, AI-enhanced e-participation tools aim

to process large volumes of input, cluster arguments, generate summaries, and structure debate, addressing long-standing challenges of scale and coordination in democratic deliberation [3, 4]. Yet, the integration of AI into civic technologies raises persistent concerns about inclusiveness, explainability, accountability, and institutional uptake [5–7]. Without mechanisms ensuring that AI-mediated contributions meaningfully influence decision-making, digital participation risks remaining symbolic rather than transformative. Moreover, barriers such as digital literacy gaps, infrastructural inequalities, and trust deficits continue to limit effective engagement [8].

At the same time, there is growing demand for more effective participation through democratic and inclusive dialogues [9–11], able to provide citizens with avenues and resources to voice their opinions and propose ideas [12]. Over recent decades, public participation has become a central strategy for governments seeking to enhance the legitimacy, trust, and transparency of decision-making [13, 14]. E-participation platforms and civic technologies are increasingly leveraged to streamline interactions between government and society [15–18], with the dual aim of improving the effectiveness of policies by strengthening public engagement [19, 20].

Despite these advances, many e-participation initiatives have failed to meet expectations or achieve their intended democratic outcomes [21], leading to criticisms for limited success in engaging underrepresented groups [22, 23], low user participation [24–27], and persistent digital divides that exclude citizens lacking digital skills or access [28, 29]. Against this backdrop, the design research community has turned renewed attention to Participatory Design (PD) as a means of shaping AI technologies in line with democratic values.

Delgado et al. [30] describe this as a ‘participatory turn’ in AI design, increasingly inviting stakeholders into design and governance processes. Yet, their analysis shows participation is still unevenly enacted: some initiatives restrict involvement to labeling data or validating models, while others experiment with deeper forms of co-creation and power-sharing. The challenge therefore extends beyond involving diverse publics. It concerns ensuring that participatory processes translate into socio-technical arrangements where stakeholder voices tangibly influence and meaningfully shape how AI systems are designed, deployed, and governed. Scholars argue that AI requires a multilevel socio-technical approach, where technology is inseparable from its institutional, political, and cultural embedding [31, 32]. This need is captured by Maas and Moreno Inglés [33], who introduce the notion of ‘participation teeth’, emphasizing that meaningful participatory AI depends on institutional and economic arrangements capable of reducing the arbitrariness of developers’ power and redistributing control toward stakeholders.

In light of these debates, this paper examines how PD can inform the design and implementation of AI-enhanced e-participation tools and platforms. Here, civic

technologies are understood as digital infrastructures that mediate interaction between people and public institutions, including e-participation platforms designed to support participation in different ways. We address this question through the experience conducted in the Horizon Europe project ORBIS (GA: 101094765) and its six pilot cases, which brought together organizations running deliberative initiatives, their communities, and developers to co-design and test AI functionalities for AI-enhanced deliberation. Rather than positioning participation as a preliminary consultation stage, ORBIS embedded PD throughout the project lifecycle, including the integration of AI components into ongoing deliberative practices and their iterative refining in collaboration with diverse stakeholders. This approach enabled real-world observation of how technological configuration and civic processes co-evolved.

2 Theoretical background

2.1 Criticalities in AI and Democratic Deliberation

AI is increasingly adopted for smoothing citizens' interaction with democratic institutions. Tools for argument mining, discourse clustering, summarization, and visualization have been tested to process large-scale citizen input in participatory budgeting, online petitions, and public consultations [3, 34, 35]. Yet, although these systems promise efficiency and scalability, they also risk exacerbating existing biases, especially if deployed without attention to inclusivity and accountability [5, 7, 36, 37]. Algorithmic systems in the public sector have already produced examples of exclusion and harm, such as biased welfare allocation or opaque automated decision-making [38, 39]. Based on such examples, scholars warn that without mechanisms in place to ensure explainability and contestability, such tools may erode rather than strengthen democratic legitimacy [5, 40]. These critiques underscore the need to design AI-enhanced tools and platforms not only for technical efficiency but for ensuring adherence with democratic values and overall accountability.

2.2. The Participatory Turn in AI Design

In response to such concerns, the literature has deeply vetted pros and cons of participatory approaches to AI design. Delgado et al. [30] conceptualize this 'participatory turn' through four dimensions: goals (why participation is needed), scope (what is open to negotiation), participants (who is involved), and methods (how participation is enacted). This study also frames the diversity and unevenness

of current practices. As a result, different schools of thought—ranging from user-centered design to co-creation, value-sensitive design, and deliberative democracy—are now converging in AI research, but also by exposing persistent risks. While many initiatives treat participation instrumentally—aimed at improving system accuracy or usability—only a minority pursue its intrinsic democratic value, grounding participation in the right of affected communities to inform and thus shape technologies that govern their lives [30, 41]. Arnstein's [42] ladder of participation remains a key reference: only higher rungs, associated with stakeholder power and control, can realize the emancipatory promise of participatory AI [43].

However, critics warn that current practices too often remain superficial. Participation-washing—in which consultation is used to legitimize pre-defined agendas—risks reproducing colonial and corporate power structures [43, 44]. Himmelreich [45] has even questioned whether participatory AI rests on weak normative grounds, arguing that its costs may outweigh its benefits. Counterarguments emphasize that AI's deep entanglement with social systems creates coercive effects that justify democratic oversight [33, 46].

2.3. Socio-Technical Perspectives and Power Asymmetries

The literature increasingly stresses the need to move beyond narrow and isolated participatory exercises toward socio-technical approaches that acknowledge how AI is embedded in border structures [31, 32]. Within this discourse, Maas and Moreno Inglés [33] argue that participatory AI should address two mostly neglected dimensions: (1) the legal-institutional arrangements for ensuring that participation has binding consequence and operationalize, and (2) the political economy of AI production, which tends to concentrate power in a few corporate actors [47, 48]. Without tackling such structural asymmetries, participation risks remaining at the developers' discretion—what Pettit [49] terms 'arbitrary power', where participation depends on the discretionary goodwill of decision-makers rather than on institutional guarantees. For civic technologies, this implies that co-design cannot be limited to collecting user input, but should rather consider how institutions adopt and operationalize citizen contributions [50, 51]. Deliberative democracy theory emphasizes that empowerment is not achieved merely by granting citizens a voice, but by ensuring that their contributions exert genuine influence over collective decisions [52]. In e-participation, this implies designing AI-enhanced tools that facilitate feedback loops, institutional accountability, and systemic uptake.

2.4. Current Directions of PD for AI

Lastly, a relevant stream of literature highlights the experimentations between PD and AI technologies. Muller and Liao [53] discuss how participatory design fictions can foster ethical reflection among both communities and developers; Donia and Shaw [54] emphasize reciprocal knowledge exchange in co-designing ethical AI; and Fernández-Martínez et al. [55] propose combining collective intelligence and AI in co-designed participatory tools to strengthen these reciprocal processes. More recently, novel co-creation formats such as the “prompt-a-thon” have been explored to integrate generative AI into participatory design practices [56], while citizen science approaches are being mobilized to co-create and evaluate democratic AI solutions [57]. At the same time, critical perspectives caution that participation alone cannot serve as a design remedy for the limitations of machine learning and AI, but require to be embedded within structural conditions that prevent superficial engagement or extractive dynamics [44].

The existing scholarship documents a wide range of participatory formats, co-creation practices, and reciprocal exchanges in AI design. The debates indicate that PD for AI should not be conceived as a site of technical problem-solving and refinement, but as a setting for learning as a two-way process: participants and communities gain literacy about the affordances and limitations of AI technologies, while designers and developers gain insight into the social practices, values, and institutional constraints that shape responsible deployment. This learning is typically described as an implicit outcome of participatory practices rather than conceptualized as emerging from specific socio-technical configurations. This view resonates with the Scandinavian PD tradition, which emphasizes organizational learning and the renegotiation of expertise [51, 58]. However, its application to AI-mediated civic technologies remains empirically fragmented and theoretically underdeveloped.

2.5 Research Gap and Research Question

Despite the expanding literature on PD for AI, several gaps remain. First, most studies focus on isolated engagement practices, overlooking how PD operates as an ongoing organizational and infrastructural practice within AI-enhanced civic technologies [33], rather than across the lifecycle of AI-enhanced civic infrastructures development. Second, while the participatory turn in AI design has clarified goals, scope, participants, and methods [30], it has paid less attention to how participatory insights are institutionally taken up and embedded in long-term programs and how this embedding reshapes both technological architectures and deliberative routines. Third, while the literature documents PD practices and instances of reciprocal exchange, it does not conceptualize PD as a socio-technical

mediation process that operates longitudinally between communities, public-sector organizations, and AI developers. As a result, the field lacks an intermediate theoretical account of how PD can unfold for AI-enhanced deliberation beyond isolated participatory interventions.

This paper addresses this gap by asking: *How does Participatory Design operate as a socio-technical mediation mechanism between differentiated deliberative practices and AI affordances in the development of AI-enhanced civic technologies?*

3 Methodology

To answer this question, we propose an intermediate theoretical account of PD as a socio-technical mediation mechanism. Building upon Delgado et al.'s [30] analytical dimensions of the participatory turn—goals, scope, participants, and methods—as a structured framework for examining how participation is configured in AI design. Their framework provides a clear set of parameters for articulating why participation is undertaken, what is open to negotiation, who is involved, and how participation unfolds. In this paper, we adopt these dimensions as analytical anchors and extend them to the specific context of AI-enhanced deliberation, where AI systems actively mediate interaction, representation, and sensemaking. This paper adopts Delgado et al.'s [30] dimensions not as evaluative categories, but as analytical entry points to reconceptualize how PD acts as a mediation process. In doing so, we move from describing participation along a spectrum of agency to explaining how participatory configurations are negotiated, recalibrated, and embedded in AI-enhanced civic technologies.

The proposed account conceptualizes PD supports the design and development of AI-enhanced deliberation tools and platforms through dynamic mediation configurations across four interrelated intersections.

- *Why is participation needed?* → *Goals × Deliberative Purpose*
Participation goals in AI-enhanced deliberation are not homogeneous but articulated through differentiated deliberative purposes—such as collective contribution, spontaneous discussion, informed decision-making, or strategic planning. Each purpose generates distinct socio-technical demands on AI systems, ranging from aggregation affordances and clustering capabilities to infrastructural flexibility, traceability, and institutional translation capacity. PD operates as the mediation space in which these purposes are made explicit and translated into AI design orientations.
- *What is on the table?* → *Scope × AI Configuration*.
Through PD, the configuration of AI components can expand what becomes negotiable within deliberative processes. In AI-enhanced

deliberation, this may range from specific AI functions to interface design, reporting formats, and pathways for policy translation. AI configuration can, in turn, expand what becomes negotiable within deliberative processes, reshaping not only technical components but also the boundaries of deliberation itself—what can be expressed, aggregated, visualized, and acted upon.

- *Who is involved? → Participants × Role Reconfiguration.*
PD for AI-enhanced deliberation reconfigures roles within deliberative processes. Different actors contribute distinct forms of expertise: deliberative practitioners bring situated knowledge of deliberative practices and community dynamics; developers contribute technical specifications and architectural constraints; designers mediate between civic and computational logics across different design phases; institutional actors provide insight into embedding, adoption, and potential scaling. Participation thus becomes the structured setting in which these heterogeneous forms of knowledge are surfaced, aligned, negotiated, and partially redistributed.
- *What form does stakeholder participation take? → Methods × Iterative Evolution.*
PD unfolds as an iterative process rather than a discrete event. Workshops surface needs and generate initial prototypes, up to their validation. Prototypes produce frictions—such as adoption challenges, infrastructural constraints, or institutional misalignments—that trigger modification and recalibration of both AI-enhanced tools and deliberative practices. PD operates as the mechanism through which AI-enhanced e-participation is continuously adjusted in response to contextual demands.

Across these intersections, PD is conceptualized as a structured, multilayered socio-technical mediation process that aligns differentiated deliberative purposes with AI affordances and institutional conditions over time. This intermediate theoretical account provides an analytical lens through which the development of AI-enhanced deliberation can be examined beyond isolated participatory interventions. Methodologically, the study builds on the Scandinavian Participatory Design tradition, emphasizing stakeholder empowerment, iterative engagement, and the analysis of socio-technical arrangements [59, 50, 51].

3.1 Empirical setting: The ORBIS Project

The empirical study was conducted within the Horizon Europe project ORBIS, which developed and piloted four AI-enhanced components—Argument Mining, Feedback Aggregation, Explanation Generator, and Policy Recommendation—integrated into three e-participation platforms. These components collectively

formed the ORBIS Toolkit¹ and were iteratively co-designed and tested in real-world deliberative settings. The experimentation took place on three platforms:

- PolisOrbis (polisorbis.copernicani.it), built on the open-source Pol.is engine, designed for large-scale participation, visualizes emerging opinion clusters in real-time.
- BCause (bcause.app) focuses on structured discussions, organized into pro and con positions, visualized through timelines and argument trees; it also generates summaries and identifies key insights that advance discussions.
- Democratic Reflection (democratic-reflection.web.app) harnesses real-time audience feedback over live or video recorded events, using visual analytics to provide insights on the audience position against the ongoing discussion.

Since its outset, the research involved five organizations running six democratic engagement experiments across different scales and domains (Fig. 1). These pilots provided heterogeneous deliberative contexts—ranging from structured policy-oriented processes to more spontaneous community-based discussions—within which AI-enhanced tools were co-designed, adapted, and embedded. This diversity offered a valuable comparative setting for examining how PD mediated between differentiated deliberative purposes and AI affordances across institutional environments.

	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6
REIMAGINING THE BUILDING BLOCKS OF DEMOCRACY	TEENS FOR DEMOCRACY	YOUNG THINKERS AND EU DECISION-MAKERS	FUTURE4CITIZENS	TRANSITION MECHANISMS FOR A DEMOCRATIC CITY	ALLIANCE FOR ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND DEVELOPMENT IN WESTERN GREECE	
Organiz.	Democracy and Culture Foundation	Democracy and Culture Foundation	Center for European Policy Studies	Re-Imagine Europa	Rob De Matt	Perifereia Dytiki Ellada
Scale	International	Initially European, to scale out to a global level	European	Initially national, to scale out to a European level	Initially local, to scale out to the national and EU level	Initially regional, to scale out to the national level
Organizing team size	2 persons from the organization team	2 persons from the organization team	4 to 5 persons from the organization team	4 persons from the organization team	3 persons from the organization team	2 persons from the organization team
Pilot features and communities	Engagement of a broad external network of partners such as the newDemocracy Foundation, Future Consensus Institute, Konrad Adenauer Foundation, Sapienship, and The Bertelsmann Foundation; to be broadly promoted through the Athens Democracy Forum	Participation of teenagers (13-17 years old) in deliberative processes carried out within the municipal councils of 5 European municipalities; collaboration with Sapienship to set up an edutainment document on democracy that will be launched under the auspices of UNICEF	Young people engage in deliberative processes with high-level EU policymakers and leading experts in the field of Citizen Science and Public Participation; built on the successful Young Thinkers initiative carried out by CEPS to be widely promoted through the annual CEPS Ideas Lab	Series of citizen dialogues with prominent foundations, focusing on issues such as inequality and fiscal reform, and the role of innovation for SDGs, employing a narrative methodology and a variation on SITRA's Futures Frequency Workshop method	Inclusion of less skilled and marginalized segments of local civil society and group of activists; participants of multicultural origin, high percentage of young and elderly residents, institutionalization of deliberative processes between civil society and local authority; focus on urban planning issues	Deliberations at the regional level involving diverse types of stakeholders; positive attitude of stakeholders to wide and inclusive participatory processes on innovation actions; focus on social and female entrepreneurship issues

Fig. 1. ORBIS's six pilots (P) and their features

¹ For a detailed technical description of the ORBIS Toolkit and how co-design informed each component respectively see Anastasiou et al. [60] and Mariani et al. [61].

requirement prioritization, externalizing tacit workflows and identifying insertion points for AI functionalities.

Two main workshop cycles (July–October 2023; April–May 2024) articulated deliberative purposes, identified user requirements, and explored AI configurations (Fig. 3). Their timing aligned with the development trajectory of AI components, allowing initial elicitation before implementation and refinement after prototype testing. Thirty-five participants from pilot organizations and their communities engaged in the first cycle, fifteen in the second, alongside six to eight consortium members. Participants were recruited through pilot networks. Workshops were facilitated by the coordination team (Politecnico di Milano and Open University), composed of design researchers specialising in AI and deliberation. Sessions combined structured framing of deliberative objectives and AI components, collaborative mapping of practices and challenges, elicitation of needs (e.g., Mentimeter polling), and collective synthesis. Miro boards supported stakeholder mapping, articulation of deliberative practices, scaling considerations, and requirement prioritisation, externalising tacit workflows and identifying insertion points for AI functionalities.

Fig. 3. Structure of the two main workshop cycles: interactions and outputs.

Co-design was supported by *shared tools and collaborative boards* that structured mediation across phases. The first workshop cycle combined mapping exercises: reflection on current practices using the live polling Mentimeter; collaborative mapping of challenges and aspirations (Miro boards; approx. 30 entries per workshop); technology demonstrations (short demos of platforms); “Magic wand” and “fill in the blanks” exercises to elicit explicit needs, fears, and expectations. The

second series used collective boards for user journey reconstruction, scenario prototyping, and requirement prioritisation exercises. Additional collaborative tools were used along the project—eg: collaborative Miro boards for stakeholder mapping, articulation of deliberative practices, identification of scaling directions (Fig. 4), and clustering of challenges and aspirations.

Fig. 4. Example of pilot activity mapping and AI integration points.

Following initial workshops, structured Excel templates supported co-creation and coordination, operating as *longitudinal mediation infrastructures*. Two artefacts as shared google sheets were central: *Implementation Plans* (Appendix II) used to design and iteratively revise deliberative stages, target audiences, AI functionalities, and expected outputs; and *Pilot Diaries* (Appendix III), completed after deliberative activities to document participation dynamics, inclusion efforts, AI inclusion and reception, and procedural adjustments. Beyond documentation and data collection, the diaries activated reflexive practices within pilot organisations, encouraging critical assessment of deliberative evolution over time.

In parallel, AI development evolved through recurrent biweekly meetings with multiple cross-domain representatives—between Feb 2023 and Jan 2026: 60 pilot coordination meetings engaging 10 organisations; 38 technical meetings with 6 organisations; 34 pilot–technical alignment meetings with 6 pilots and at least 2 representatives. These meetings functioned as mediation spaces in which deliberative goals were translated into technical specifications, interpretability challenges and infrastructural constraints were debated, and adjustments negotiated. Frictions—such as emergent registration barriers, opaque AI outputs, or policy translation limits—triggered iterative revision and implementation of

components including Argument Mining, Feedback Aggregation, Explanation Generator, and Policy Recommendation.

Through this distributed configuration of workshops, artefacts, and recurrent meetings, co-design operated as a sustained socio-technical mediation process.

3.3 Data collection from co-design moments

Table 1 provides an overview of the main data sources used to gather data, the type of material collected, and their role in the analysis. Data was triangulated, allowing a comparison of insights from workshops, meetings, deliberative experiments, and project documentation.

Table 1. Overview of data sources, their use and contribution in the analysis.

Data source	Time frame	Engagement	Data Collected	Contribution against account dimensions
Preliminary case study analysis of 6 pilots	Jan–Mar 2023	Pilot organisations; debate facilitators; citizen/community representatives	4,400 words (written materials) + 5,400 words (presentation transcripts). Profiles of objectives, democratic attitudes, deliberative practices, interests, and scope (Appendix I).	Identification of differentiated deliberative purposes and contextual needs (Goals dimension)
Co-design workshops (multi-stakeholder, online & in-person)	<i>1st series of 6, July 2023</i>	35 participants across pilots, with communities members and facilitators	6 workshops (2h each); Miro boards; Mentimeter polling; observation notes. Mapping of practices, roles, challenges.	Articulation of deliberative purposes; translation into initial user requirements; expansion of negotiable scope (Goals × Scope)
	<i>Oct 2023</i>	26 participants from the consortium	Half-day prioritisation and refinement of user requirements and AI functionalities; observation notes.	Alignment between deliberative needs and AI configuration decisions (Scope × AI Configuration)
	<i>2nd series of 9, Apr–May 2024</i>	6 pilot-specific with 15 participants + 3 follow-up with consortium members	User scenarios; refined requirements; deliberative alignment; scaling trajectories; technological options; researcher notes.	Refinement of mediation configurations; integration of institutional embedding considerations (Scope × Participants)

Observations of biweekly meetings	<i>Feb 2023-Jan 2026 (60 meetings)</i>	WP leaders, including pilot organisations; consortium cross-domain experts	1.5h meetings; observation notes and minutes documenting deliberative updates and AI tool adaptation.	Longitudinal tracing of mediation episodes; review of AI tools in response to practice (Methods × Iterative Evolution)
Biweekly meetings with developers	<i>June 2024-Jan 2026 (38 meetings)</i>	Tech-experts; AI developers; designers; coordination team	1h discussions each; observation notes on refinement of AM, FA, EG, PR; usability, ethics, platform implementation.	Negotiation between technical affordances and deliberative constraints (Scope × Participants)
Biweekly meetings with pilots	<i>June 2024-Jan 2026 (34 meetings)</i>	Pilots organisation and facilitators; coordination team; Tech representatives	1h meetings; observation notes on implementation progress and AI integration into deliberative activities, and unmet needs.	Documentation of role reconfiguration and adjustment of deliberative workflows (Participants × Methods)
Project documentation	Continuous	Consortium-wide	Supplemented primary data (Appendix III); documentation of iterative development (Appendix II).	Material evidence of iterative calibration and institutional embedding across pilots

These heterogeneous materials were triangulated to construct a unified dataset capturing the evolution of AI-enhanced deliberation tools and associated deliberative practices over time. Triangulation also included materials produced during the co-design process, such as MIRO boards and Excel sheets containing (i) implementation plans of pilots’ deliberative experiments (Appendix II) and (ii) pilot diaries with pilots’ reflections (Appendix III). Additional sources included project deliverables, reports, and field notes. All these materials were consolidated, cross-checked, and validated to build a unified dataset for analysis.

3.4 Data analysis stages

Given the study’s conceptual framing of PD as a socio-technical mediation mechanism (Section 2.5), the unit of analysis was defined as *mediation episodes*—instances in which deliberative purposes, AI affordances, and institutional constraints were explicitly negotiated, recalibrated, or reconfigured. Such episodes were identified across workshop interactions, technical discussions, implementation meetings, and artefact revisions. Analysis proceeded in three stages.

Stage 1: Within-case analysis. Each pilot was examined independently as a case to reconstruct:

- deliberative purposes and expectations;
- user requirements emerging from workshops and meetings;
- AI functionalities prioritised, modified, or contested;
- observed frictions (e.g., interpretability challenges, infrastructural constraints, institutional misalignments);
- adjustments in roles, workflows, or implementation strategies.

The result is a detailed view of how co-design unfolded in each deliberative context.

Stage 2: Cross-Case Synthesis. Findings from individual pilots were compared to identify recurring patterns and context-specific variations. Particular attention was given to how different deliberative purposes generated differentiated demands on AI configuration and how these were addressed—or remained partially unresolved—across pilots operating at different scales and institutional settings.

Stage 3: Theory-guided coding. To connect empirical observations to the proposed intermediate theoretical account, coding was structured around the four analytical intersections introduced in Section 2.5:

- Goals × Deliberative Purposes (how differentiated deliberative aims shaped AI expectations);
- Scope × AI Configuration (what became negotiable in relation to AI functions and interfaces);
- Participants × Role Reconfiguration (how actor roles shifted across mediation processes);
- Methods × Iterative Evolution (how workshops, meetings, and implementation cycles enabled revision and recalibration over time).

Coding moved iteratively between descriptive categories (e.g., clustering needs, reporting requirements, access barriers) and analytical constructs (e.g., mediation, friction, recalibration, institutional embedding, mutual learning). This abductive approach allowed empirical material to inform and refine the conceptual account.

4 Findings: PD as Socio-Technical Mediation in AI-Enhanced Deliberation

The findings below are the result of the theory-guided coding stage described above. Through a cross-pilot analysis, they explore how PD functions as the mediating mechanism across the four interrelated intersections of goals, scope, participants, and methods.

4.1 Goals × Deliberative Purposes. Insights on deliberative attitudes and needs

Across the six pilots, participation was articulated through differentiated and heterogeneous deliberative purposes that co-design made explicit and operational. Early workshop mapping revealed that what 'participation' means varies significantly: some pilots seek structured policy input, others aim at open civic dialogue, while others focus on building long-term strategic influence. This produced seven inductive clusters of how pilots and their communities expect participation to occur and support deliberative purposes—summarize in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Clusters of deliberative purposes and related needs, and their relation to ORBIS pilots (P) as a result of the first series of co-design workshops

These findings became analytical anchors to structure functional and interactional requirements for AI-enhanced deliberation across pilots. Cross-pilot comparison resulted in their consolidation into five structured needs that capture recurring patterns of deliberative needs and expectations, functioning as structured pathways for aligning civic expectations with AI affordances, thus guiding AI development:

- *Support transitions from open dialogue to reflective deliberation*, in both spontaneous and structured settings.
- *Collective contribution at scale*, requiring mechanisms for aggregating and synthesising large volumes of input without erasing diversity.
- *Evidence-informed decision-making*, supported by summaries, argument mapping, clustering, and visualisation.
- *Accountability and traceability*, enabling participants to follow how contributions evolve into outputs and recommendations.

- *Strategic planning and policy conversion*, as support in translating deliberation into institutional influence, equally relevant for pilots operating at different governance levels.

Policy-oriented pilots (P1, P3) framed participation primarily in terms of accountability and institutional impact. Their deliberative purpose goes beyond discussion, aiming at generating outputs that could feed into policy debates. In line with research on e-participation legitimacy [62, 63], this translated into demands for traceability: participants wanted to see how contributions moved from discussion to recommendation. In one pilot, organisers explicitly expressed concern that without visible linkage between debate and policy output, the process would be perceived as symbolic. This demand directly shaped the redesign of the Policy Recommendation component into an interactive output linked to underlying contributions.

Local pilots (P5, P6) prioritized ease of access, local language interfaces, and the ability to blend in-person and digital contributions seamlessly, consistent with earlier findings on community-driven participation [22, 27]. As community-rooted, P5 prioritised spontaneous exchange and relational engagement rather than formalised decision-making. Organisers highlighted that participants valued informal expression and narrative storytelling. When early AI outputs appeared overly structured, concerns emerged that the platform might prematurely “discipline” discussion. Co-design mediated this tension by recalibrating user journeys, integrating transcript capture for hybrid sessions, and softening structured interfaces to preserve openness while enabling later aggregation.

Complementarity, global-scale pilots (P2, P4) feature deliberative purposes that involve aggregating dispersed inputs across time, geographies, and even publics. Here, scale introduced specific challenges: large input volumes risked flattening diversity and nuances of perspectives. While benefitting from clustering to aggregate contributions, these pilots revealed anxiety that minority perspectives might disappear within clusters. As a result, explainability and visualisation features were treated not as optional add-ons but as safeguards for pluralism.

Across contexts, inclusiveness emerged as a cross-cutting goal, yet its meaning varied. O6 as a rural pilot flagged infrastructural barriers: mobile incompatibility and registration complexity limited participation from new farmers. In youth-focused settings as in P2 and P4, participants were enthusiastic but required additional facilitation to translate informal exchanges into AI-processable inputs. Then, all pilots stressed that inclusion cannot be equated with more volume of inputs: it requires curating and elevating substantive contributions, mitigating the risks of biased or skewed perspectives while fostering informed participation [9, 28].

A recurring cross-pilot concern regarded the deliberative weight of contributions. While all voices were considered legitimate, organisers repeatedly questioned whether all inputs carried equal argumentative value. Particularly in

large-scale discussions, participants worried that clustering and aggregation mechanisms might treat loosely formulated comments and carefully argued contributions as equivalent units. As one pilot noted during a coordination meeting, the challenge was to remain open and plural without allowing discussion to dissolve into noise. This tension points to a central dilemma of AI-enhanced deliberation: how to combine inclusiveness with epistemic quality. Pilots described this as a delicate balance to achieve—deliberation should remain open and accessible, yet also coherent and productive. In this sense, AI-supported aggregation required not only technical optimisation but careful calibration of how arguments are grouped, summarized, and visualized. This concern aligns with discussions on curated knowledge exchange (Christiansson et al., 2024), which emphasize that democratic deliberation depends not simply on volume of input but on meaningful structuring of contributions. It further echoes prior analyses cautioning that participatory platforms risk losing legitimacy either by over-restricting participation or by allowing unstructured contributions to undermine deliberative quality [23, 64].

Within ORBIS, co-design functioned as where these tensions were negotiated. Rather than automating filtration, researchers, developers and pilots opted for moderation strategies, explainability layers, and interface adjustments that could preserve plurality while enhancing interpretive clarity. In this way, PD mediated between inclusiveness and epistemic structuring, making explicit the trade-offs involved in AI-supported deliberation. It also revealed structural limits: while collective contribution and structured dialogue were effectively supported by aggregation tools, strategic planning and institutional influence required substantial human interpretation beyond AI-generated outputs. Overall, PD operated not just as a guarantee of alignment, but as a mechanism for negotiating the degree and conditions under which AI affordances could meaningfully support varied deliberative practice.

4.2 Scope × AI Configuration. Informing e-participation platform and AI-enhanced tools

If Section 4.1 showed what pilots expected AI-enhanced participation to achieve, this section examines how those expectations translated into a shifting scope of co-design. Scope refers to where and to what depth co-design could shape AI-enhanced tools and platforms—namely, which aspects of AI components, outputs, and integrations were open to reconfiguration, and how these boundaries evolved in response to pilot needs and implementation frictions. ORBIS introduces AI in e-participation settings to address structural challenges of deliberative democracy, also confirmed across pilots: managing large volumes of input, structuring complex debates, enabling hybrid online–offline participation, and supporting traceable translation into policy recommendations. AI components became progressively

embedded within deliberative workflows, actively shaping interaction, aggregation, and output formation. Co-design therefore operated both on AI components and through them, as pilots encountered and responded to AI-mediated structuring effects.

In early workshops, pilots articulated needs in experiential terms—'avoid dominance', 'make everyone visible', 'ensure discussion leads somewhere', 'keep debates coherent'. Through co-design with HCI and AI developers, these were translated into concrete configuration questions: How should clustering group arguments? What counts as analyzable input? How should explanations be presented? How can summaries remain faithful to variety and nuances of positions?

In parallel, community-rooted pilots such as P5 highlighted spontaneity and relational engagement as central, stressing how structured outputs initially risked constraining informal exchange. Additionally, both P5 (with participants of very diverse ages and digital literacy) and P6 (engaging farmers and agri-related SMEs) pointed out digital access barriers limiting participation. All pilots also highlighted the need to consider multi-step deliberations, sometimes mixing online and offline participation. Co-design led to interface adjustments softened rigid structuring, but most importantly to the introduction of transcript upload and integrated Argument Mining (AM) to process in-person sessions into digital workflows. What began as a feature request became an infrastructural extension of scope, allowing AI to operate across in-person and digital interactions. It thus responded to needs that had not been fully anticipated during early requirements elicitation.

In policy-oriented pilots (P1, P3), scope expanded toward output legitimacy. Early Policy Recommendation PR outputs judged overly generic. Organisers insisted on visible grounding in participant inputs. PR was therefore retooled to link recommendations to argument clusters and underlying inputs as source contributions. Nonetheless, institutional actors still edited outputs prior to formal use, highlighting scope limits: AI could synthesize, not wholly replace, policy translation.

The Explanation Generator most clearly shows how scope deepened through friction. The original Explanation Generator presented heatmaps of term relevance; P1, P2, P4 found these opaque: 'scientific but detached from meaning'. The issue was not accuracy but interpretability. Iterative mediation shifted explainability from model transparency toward communicative intelligibility: The component was re-engineered to produce narrative explanations tying clusters to specific contributions. This is a clear case where friction drove a deeper epistemic reconfiguration rather than a cosmetic UI change.

Multilingual affordances, repeatedly requested by local-focused pilots (P5, P6), remained only partially implemented due to technical and resource constraints. This exposed the bounded nature of participatory influence over AI architecture.

Platform-level adaptations emerged from these negotiations rather than predefinition. PolisOrbis refined polling and synthesis pathways to connect large-scale opinion capture with possible actionable outputs. BCause refined stance-sharing to balance structure and accessibility, and integrated transcript import to capture live deliberations and its structured processing integrating Argument Mining. Democratic Reflection developed complementary visual dashboards: one to assist moderators in identifying convergence and polarisation during live sessions, the others for participants to see how the audience is positioning against the ongoing discussion.

Table 2 maps the deliberative alignment pathways identified in Section 4.1 to the clustered operational requirements articulated through co-design and the corresponding AI functionalities implemented across platforms. This mapping shows how deliberative purposes were progressively translated into configurable AI components.

Table 2. Co-designed user requirements and their operationalization into Toolkit and platforms functionalities—adapted from Mariani et al. [61]. AM = Argument Mining; FA = Feedback Aggregator; EG = Explanation Generator; PR = Policy Recommendation. For more details see Anastasiou et al. [60].

Deliberative Alignment Pathway (as section 4.1)	Operational requirements (clustered)	Support toward deliberative objectives to inform AI	AI functionalities in ORBIS
Collective contribution at scale	Efficient brainstorming and idea management	Maintain momentum by clustering and prioritizing ideas.	FA extracts and clusters ideas; AM analyzes topics and interconnections among participants' viewpoints.
	Real-time data analysis	Track directions and detect polarizations.	BCause and Democratic Reflection capture live inputs; AM + FA provide processed outputs for visualization of positions and diversity.
Open dialogue & reflective deliberation	Enhanced discussion management	Structure complex debates by organizing opinions by topic and threads by stance (pro/against).	BCause structures discussions in threads; Democratic Reflection analyses discourses with inputs from participants; AM + FA jointly extract, cluster, and summarize arguments.
	Asynchronous and synchronous interaction support	Combine in-person and online inputs seamlessly.	Transcripts uploaded into BCause ; Democratic Reflection embeds transcripts from live or recorded debates; processed by AM + FA .
	Integration of visual inputs	Facilitate comprehension of complex debates through visualizations.	BCause and PolisOrbis provide visualizations (topic clusters, stance graphs) based on AM/FA outputs, released upon moderator verification.
	Facilitation and moderation support	Prevent dominance by few actors, ensure	BCause includes features for stance-sharing; FA clusters discourses to highlight diversity of positions.

		inclusiveness, and identify conflict early.	
Evidence-informed decision-making	Reporting and summarizing	Provide structured summaries and consensus points.	FA produces topic-specific summaries; AM structures arguments relations.
Accountability & traceability	Transparent and trustworthy AI processes	Clarify how outputs are generated.	EG explains AM/FA processes in plain language, and on what contributions PR is grounding recommendations.
Strategic planning & policy conversion	Policy conversion and actionable outputs	Translate deliberations into tangible outcomes.	PR transforms AM/FA outputs into actionable policy recommendations grounded in deliberative inputs.

Once integrated into deliberative settings, AI-enhanced clustering, summarisation, visualisation, and recommendation mechanisms actively structured interaction by influencing what became visible, prioritised, and actionable. Co-design therefore unfolded recursively: negotiated configurations were deployed, their effects observed, features and settings recalibrated or even reviewed.

Scope × AI Configuration captures an evolving perimeter of PD influence over AI development. In some cases, scope expanded (e.g., explanation redesign, hybrid transcript integration); in others, it remained constrained (e.g., multilingual implementation, policy automation). PD did not guarantee alignment but continuous negotiation of how far AI affordances could meaningfully support differentiated deliberative practices and needs.

4.3 Participants × Role Reconfiguration. Mediations among disciplines and practices

Integrating AI into deliberation reconfigured roles and redistributed interpretive authority among developers, designers, facilitators, institutional actors, and community representatives: it altered who was able to interpret, validate, and shape deliberative outputs, and under what conditions. In these terms, a fundamental finding concerns the iterative adjustment between developers, designers, and pilot organisations.

Early co-design processes surfaced initial asymmetries of expectation: many organisers expected near-ready AI solutions, while developers assumed higher baseline technical literacy. Developers, conversely, often assumed a higher baseline of technical literacy among civic actors. These mismatches of expectations surfaced during co-creation workshops, generating moments of friction that required structured mediation. Practical consequences and role shifts followed. Developers quickly realised that abstract explanations of functionalities were insufficient, moving to make technology tangible and experientially grounded through early prototyping and demonstrations. Still, such role reconfiguration was uneven across pilots. In P5, which included a team member with strong technical expertise, AI integration progressed more fluidly, identifying insertion points for clustering and

summarisation from the outset, and incorporating AI components directly into workflow planning.

Also pilots acquired initially not foreseen roles. P1, P2, and P4 contributed their own deliberative transcripts to participate in AI fine-tuning for generating clustered arguments and summaries based on familiar debate material. This strategy reduced abstraction and enabled organisers to evaluate AI outputs in relation to their real deliberative practice, making visible both the potential and the limits of AI mediation.

In this process, researchers assumed the role of translators, who converted deliberative needs into artefacts (user journeys, scenarios, templates), framed technical constraints in accessible terms, and adjusted facilitation methods to maintain shared understanding. This mediation extended into coordination and technical meetings where misunderstandings were iteratively revisited. Co-design extended beyond continuous redesign of interaction formats, explanation strategies, and validation procedures, concerning the design of collaboration and engagement processes as well as the configuration of technological artefacts themselves.

AI-enhancement also reconfigured facilitation roles. Clustering and summarisation tools turned facilitators from moderators of discussion to interpreters of algorithmic outputs. When clusters were presented to participants, facilitators contextualised them, clarified limitations, and reopened debate when summaries appeared reductive. AI outputs thus acquired epistemic weight, and facilitators became brokers between computational structuring and civic interpretation.

Institutional actors assumed the additional role of evaluators of legitimacy. In policy-oriented pilots, AI-generated outputs were assessed not only for internal coherence but for their suitability in institutional settings. Organisers evaluated whether outputs met standards of traceability and accountability required for policy uptake. In this sense, AI-enhanced deliberation redistributed validation authority across actors.

Through these dynamics, civic actors developed literacy about AI affordances and constraints, while developers gained insight into situated deliberative practices and institutional conditions. This mutual learning was embedded in concrete episodes of prototype testing, friction, and revision and recalibration rather than abstract exchange. Importantly, this does not eliminate asymmetries. Technical expertise remained concentrated among developers, and final implementation decisions were bound by architectural constraints. However, co-design created structured spaces in which these asymmetries could be surfaced and negotiated rather than remaining implicit.

Participants × Role Reconfiguration therefore captures how AI-enhanced deliberation altered system behaviour and the distribution of interpretive

responsibility. PD functioned as the mediation mechanism through which these role attributes were negotiated, stabilised, and occasionally contested.

4.4 Methods × Iterative Evolution. Reshaping understanding and journeys

This section examines how PD unfolded through continuous revision, tailoring, and adjustment of methods in response to frictions, implementation constraints, and emerging deliberative insights.

Initial workshop cycles surfaced deliberative purposes and generated early requirements and scenarios. Nevertheless, these scenarios also produced expectations among pilots, which then required iterative adjustment on both sides to remain feasible for AI development and e-participation platform implementation. Once prototypes were introduced into pilot contexts, new challenges emerged that demanded methodological adaptation. Early assumptions about how and when AI functionalities could be integrated often proved overly optimistic. For example, pilots initially imagined clustering and summarisation as end-of-process tools. Implementation showed that AI-summaries were shaping subsequent discussion trajectories. This prompted changes in sequencing.

Similarly, transcripts introduction for supporting deliberation in hybrid settings required pilots to modify both deliberative processes and facilitation routines. What had previously been spontaneous in-person exchange needed structured documentation to become analysable input. This triggered procedural adjustments—assigning note-takers, standardising recording practices, and allocating time for transcript validation before AI processing. Moreover, as pilots gained a clearer understanding of what counted as usable deliberative input, they increasingly prepared contributions in formats compatible with AI processing and its timing, structured sessions to enable later aggregation, and identified moments where AI-generated synthesis could be introduced without disrupting dialogue. To enable these adjustments, most pilots—apart from P5, which benefited from internal technical expertise—required intensive mediation. Additional facilitated workshop sessions supported teams in mapping deliberative stages against AI capabilities, often using Implementation Plans and User Journeys as bridging artefacts.

Participation thus shifted from needs elicitation toward workflow redesign. Implementation Plans (Appendix II) became central to this evolution: pilots mapped deliberative stages, specified intended AI functionalities, and revised timelines in light of technical feasibility and experiential feedback. Plans were updated repeatedly, reflecting shifts in scope and expectations. For instance, P3 adjusted the sequencing of policy-oriented deliberation to allow time for AI-supported synthesis before stakeholder consultation; P5 restructured community meetings to enable transcript integration and summarisation without undermining relational

dynamics; and P2 introduced intermediate reflection phases after exposure to clustered outputs, enabling participants to reassess positions before moving toward synthesis. These revisions show that methods were not static but adaptively reconfigured.

Pilot Diaries (Appendix III) further institutionalised iterative evolution. In several pilots, diary reflections prompted methodological change. In youth-focused pilots, for example, diary entries noted difficulties translating informal exchanges into structured inputs, leading to additional facilitation phases before AI processing. Reflexivity thus became embedded in participation, generating feedback loops not only between pilots and developers, but also within pilot organisations.

Across pilots, frictions were treated as drivers of change. Interpretability challenges with the Explanation Generator prompted redesign of explanation formats. Misalignment between policy expectations and AI outputs led to revised reporting templates. Delays in transcript processing triggered timeline adjustments. Rather than treating friction as failure, co-design institutionalised it as a signal for revision and recalibration. Biweekly coordination and technical meetings served as structured spaces where these signals were examined and translated into procedural or technical adjustments.

PD methods therefore evolved iteratively alongside AI configuration. Workshops became more scenario-driven and hands-on, since early abstraction proved insufficient. Prototype demonstrations became routine rather than exceptional. Alignment meetings increasingly focused on sequencing and integration, while serving also for additional feature discovery.

Methods × Iterative Evolution thus captures PD as a temporal mediation process. Co-design proceeded through cycles of exploration, implementation, friction, and revision. AI-enhanced deliberation emerged as a continuously adjusted configuration rather than a fixed artefact.

5. Discussion: PD as Socio-Technical Mediation in AI-Enhanced Deliberation

The ORBIS experience offers a set of empirically grounded lessons on how PD can support the development of AI-enhanced deliberation. The findings provide a reflection on how PD operates as a socio-technical mediation mechanism across four interrelated dimensions elaborated from how Delgado et al. [30] depicted the participatory turn in AI design: goals, scope, participants, and methods. It also shows how co-design structures the negotiation between differentiated deliberative practices and AI affordances over time, reflecting the need of continuous negotiation of socio-technical arrangements rather than episodic consultation [50, 51].

Clearly, ORBIS lessons do not constitute a prescriptive blueprint; rather, they activate points of reflection that can inform future co-design efforts in AI-enhanced civic technologies.

While the participatory turn has clarified why stakeholder engagement matters and how it may be structured [30], participation is often analysed either normatively [41, 46] or through isolated engagement formats [56, 57]. Less attention has been given to how PD operates longitudinally in contexts where AI systems actively structure deliberative interaction. By examining ORBIS across multiple pilots and iterative cycles, this study has extended that literature by showing how PD affects both deliberative practices and AI configuration in response to contextual constraints and frictions. Importantly, it shows how AI in ORBIS was not (just) an object of co-design, but acted as a structuring layer within deliberation itself, shaping visibility, interpretive authority, and sequencing of discussion. In so doing, the findings respond to concerns that participatory AI risks remaining superficial or instrumental [44], demonstrating that meaningful co-design requires negotiating how AI structures participation, not only how participation informs AI.

While ORBIS provides an empirical validation of this mediation account, yet, it does not constitute a definitive model. Rather, it offers a conceptual framing that can guide future co-design processes of AI-enhanced civic technologies and provides lessons abstracted from pilot-specific experiences toward broader applicability.

5.1 Negotiating Expectations and Literacy Gaps

A first structural lesson concerns the mismatch of expectations between practitioners and developers. As in other participatory AI settings [30], civic actors often anticipated ready-made solutions, while technical actors assumed higher levels of AI literacy. ORBIS demonstrates that such mismatches are not incidental but structural. AI-enhanced deliberation introduces epistemic asymmetries that require active mediation. Consistent with PD scholarship on bridging epistemic divides [51, 65], ORBIS shows that translation must occur both linguistically and materially. Early prototypes, transcript-based demonstrations, and iterative walkthroughs were essential in grounding abstract AI capabilities within lived deliberative practice, making them graspable and intelligible by multiple actors. This confirms insights from Donia and Shaw [54] and Muller and Liao [53], who emphasise reciprocal learning in ethical AI co-design. In addition, ORBIS extends these findings by demonstrating that such learning is not limited to workshop settings but embedded in longitudinal development cycles.

For future applications, the ORBIS experience shows that innovating AI-enhanced e-participation requires treating expectation negotiation and literacy development as core components of co-design rather than secondary outcomes.

These processes need to be grounded in hands-on engagement, enabling learning through early prototyping and demonstrations. Such an approach fosters mutual understanding and learning, and creates meaningful conditions for participation in innovation.

5.2 Institutional Uptake and Accountability

A second lesson concerns institutional embedding. Much participatory AI research focuses on engagement moments but pays limited attention to how participatory insights are operationalised within organisational routines [33]. ORBIS shows that uptake depends on whether AI functionalities are co-designed in ways that align not only with institutional validation standards and workflow structures, but first of all with deliberative values and needs. Co-designed traceability features, narrative and integrated explanations, and interactive policy outputs strengthened perceived legitimacy among pilot organisations. When AI outputs were recognisably grounded in participant contributions, adoption became more sustainable. This aligns with socio-technical accounts of empowerment that emphasise the need for non-arbitrary influence over decision-making processes [49, 62]. However, ORBIS also reveals several limits: AI-supported synthesis did not replace institutional interpretation, and strategic planning and policy translation remained necessarily human-mediated.

For future applications, the ORBIS experience indicates that institutional compatibility and operational uptake should be considered from the outset and integrated into iterative mapping processes rather than retrofitted at later stages. These factors directly affect the capacity to understand and embed AI-enhanced deliberation within organisational routines, support meaningful experimentation, and sustain iterative development over time.

5.3 Friction and Iteration for constructive Change

While early misunderstandings initially risked undermining trust, they became constructive moments of adjustment. In line with PD traditions that frame conflict and negotiation as generative forces in socio-technical development [50], frictions in ORBIS were not treated as failures but as signals requiring recalibration.

Misalignments between deliberative expectations and AI configuration surfaced repeatedly. Iterative redesign—particularly of user interfaces, user journeys, explainability mechanisms, and hybrid transcript integration—showed that PD is most effective when embedded longitudinally. Early requirements reflected partial and context-bound understandings of both deliberative practices and technological affordances. As pilots engaged with prototypes and encountered AI outputs in

practice, previously unforeseen needs emerged. Exposure to technical constraints and new capabilities reshaped expectations, revealing that alignment depends on sustained cross-disciplinary negotiation rather than one-time specification.

This dynamic supports the view that participatory AI cannot rely on isolated engagement events but benefits from institutionalised reflexive cycles [32]. From a sociotechnical perspective, AI systems are not neutral tools; they reorganise practices, responsibilities, and interpretive authority. Their design therefore requires continuous collective examination and adjustment. In ORBIS, requirements evolved through iterative exposure to prototypes, frictions prompted redesign, and deliberative workflows were repeatedly recalibrated in response to AI-mediated effects. PD thus functioned as an ongoing mechanism of reflection and reconfiguration embedded within the lifecycle of AI-enhanced deliberation.

Limitations. This study is exploratory and context-dependent. Conducted within the Horizon Europe project ORBIS, it reflects the dynamics of six pilots operating within specific institutional, cultural, and funding conditions. The pilots functioned as small-scale experimental niches [66], providing structured environments for testing co-design approaches to AI-enhanced deliberation tools under real-world constraints. While such niches enabled intensive interaction and longitudinal observation, they limit the extent to which findings can be directly generalised to other participatory AI settings. The authors' embedded role of coordinators within the project afforded privileged access to mediation processes but also introduced potential interpretive bias; triangulation across workshop artefacts, meeting documentation, transcripts, and pilot diaries, alongside reflexive analysis, was employed to mitigate this.

6. Conclusion. Toward a Transferable Mediation Framework

Conceptually, this paper extends existing accounts of the participatory turn in AI design [30] by shifting attention from participation as format to participation as longitudinal mediation infrastructure. The findings here presented require be interpreted within the limits of niche experimentation [66].

ORBIS operated as a structured experimental setting that enabled intensive observation and iterative design. Such conditions have replicability limits. However, what can be transferred is the mediation patterns identified: expectation negotiation, scope recalibration, role redistribution, and iterative methodological adjustment.

These recurring dynamics support the conceptual abstraction of PD in AI-enhanced deliberation beyond the ORBIS context. The proposed account offers an analytical and operational lens for researchers, civic technology designers, public

institutions, and innovation programmes seeking to integrate AI into participatory infrastructures. Rather than prescribing a model, it clarifies how co-design processes can be structured to surface deliberative purposes, negotiate technical constraints, redistribute interpretive authority, and institutionalise iterative recalibration.

Transferability therefore does not lie in replicating specific AI components, but in re-enacting the mediation architecture articulated in this study. The proposed account can be scaled as a reflective and structuring framework for embedding PD in AI-enhanced e-participation for deliberation. By considering where and how PD operates across goals, scope, participants, and methods, organisations can design for meaningful and longitudinal integration of AI into civic processes—not only over time, but across the institutional, technical, and interpretive dimensions that shape deliberative practice. In this sense, scaling concerns the reproducibility of mediation patterns rather than the duplication of technological artefacts.

Future research should apply this intermediate theoretical account as an analytical lens in comparative studies of initiatives developing AI-enhanced e-participation for deliberation. The four mediation dimensions identified from Delgado et al.'s—goals, scope, participants, and methods—can function as structural sites through which to examine how PD is embedded and what effects it produces in different contexts. Comparative case studies could therefore explore how PD operates across these dimensions: how participation reshapes deliberative goals; how the scope of AI configuration becomes negotiable; how roles are distributed and potentially reconfigured among civic actors, developers, and institutions; and how participatory methods evolve over time. Such analyses would make visible where mediation occurs, which dimensions become more influential or constrained under specific governance and technological conditions, and what kinds of alignment PD is able to support. Particular attention should be given to the durability of reflexive cycles beyond funded experimentation and to the minimal infrastructural conditions required to sustain longitudinal co-design. In this sense, scaling concerns not only duration, but the capacity to embed PD meaningfully across the relevant dimensions of AI-enhanced deliberation.

Fundings. The work presented in this document is funded through the project 'ORBIS. Augmenting participation, co-creation, trust and transparency in Deliberative Democracy at all scales'. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094765. However, the opinions expressed herewith are solely of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the point of view of any EU institution.

Acknowledgments. The authors would like to thank the entire ORBIS consortium for their sustained collaboration, openness, and commitment throughout the project. The richness of the experimentation and the insights presented in this paper

were made possible by the active engagement of pilot organisations, community participants, AI developers, and researchers who contributed to the co-design process along three entire years. Their willingness to reflect critically on both opportunities and frictions has been fundamental to the development of this work.

AI declaration. AI tools were employed in the preparation of this chapter solely for proofreading, language refinement, and accessibility enhancement, not for generating original content or research results. The use of AI-based proofreading support (LLM specifically) was particularly valuable given that not all the authors are non-native English speakers, ensuring improved linguistic clarity, consistency, and readability without altering the scientific meaning or interpretation of the content.

CRedit author statement. **Ilaria Mariani:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Writing – Original Draft, Writing – Review & Editing. **Francesca Rizzo:** Conceptualization, Validation, Writing – Review & Editing.

References

1. Cazacu, S., Hansen, N.B., Schouten, B.: Empowerment Approaches in Digital Civics. In: Proceedings of the 32nd Australian Conference on Human-Computer Interaction. pp. 692–699. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3441000.3441069>.
2. Duberry, J.: AI and civic tech: Engaging citizens in decision-making processes but not without risks. Presented at the June 21 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781788977319.00012>.
3. Ammitzbøll Flügge, A., Hildebrandt, T., Møller, N.H.: Street-Level Algorithms and AI in Bureaucratic Decision-Making: A Caseworker Perspective. Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact. 5, (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3449114>.
4. Rahwan, I.: Society-in-the-loop: programming the algorithmic social contract. Ethics and Information Technology. 20, 5–14 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10676-017-9430-8>.
5. Ananny, M., Crawford, K.: Seeing without knowing: Limitations of the transparency ideal and its application to algorithmic accountability. New Media & Society. 20, 973–989 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444816676645>.
6. Gebru, T.: Race and Gender. In: Dubber, M.D., Pasquale, F., and Das, S. (eds.) The Oxford Handbook of Ethics of AI. p. 0. Oxford University Press (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780190067397.013.16>.
7. Noble, S.U.: Algorithms of Oppression. New York University Press (2018). <https://doi.org/10.18574/nyu/9781479833641.001.0001>.

8. Oliveira, C., Garcia, A.C.B.: Citizens' electronic participation: a systematic review of their challenges and how to overcome them. *International Journal of Web Based Communities*. 15, 123–150 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJWBC.2019.101042>.
9. Bobbio, L.: Designing effective public participation. *Policy and Society*. 38, 41–57 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1080/14494035.2018.1511193>.
10. Henfrey, T., Feola, G., Penha-Lopes, G., Sekulova, F., Esteves, A.M.: Rethinking the sustainable development goals: Learning with and from community-led initiatives. *Sustainable Development*. 31, 211–222 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.2384>.
11. Wirtz, B.W., Weyerer, J.C., Rösch, M.: Open government and citizen participation: an empirical analysis of citizen expectancy towards open government data. *International Review of Administrative Sciences*. 85, 566–586 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020852317719996>.
12. Gascó, M.: Special Issue on Open Government: An Introduction. *Social Science Computer Review*. 33, 535–539 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1177/0894439314560676>.
13. Lourenço, R.P., Costa, J.P.: Incorporating citizens' views in local policy decision making processes. *Decision Support Systems*. 43, 1499–1511 (2007). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dss.2006.06.004>.
14. Rosenzweigova, I., Skoric, V., Asipovich, H.: Civil participation in decision-making processes: An overview of standards and practices in Council of Europe Member States (2016). <https://rm.coe.int/civil-participation-in-decision-making-processes-an-overview-of-standa/1680701801>.
15. Haro-de-Rosario, A., Sáez-Martín, A., del Carmen Caba-Pérez, M.: Using social media to enhance citizen engagement with local government: Twitter or Facebook? *New Media & Society*. 20, 29–49 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444816645652>.
16. Lindner, R., Aichholzer, G.: E-Democracy: Conceptual Foundations and Recent Trends. In: Hennen, L., van Keulen, I., Korthagen, I., Aichholzer, G., Lindner, R., and Nielsen, R.Ø. (eds.) *European E-Democracy in Practice*. pp. 11–45. Springer International, Cham, Switzerland (2020). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-27184-8_2.
17. Porumbescu, G.A.: Linking public sector social media and e-government website use to trust in government. *Government Information Quarterly*. 33, 291–304 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2016.04.006>.
18. Wukich, C.: Government Social Media Engagement Strategies and Public Roles. *Public Performance & Management Review*. 44, 187–215 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1080/15309576.2020.1851266>.
19. United Nations: United Nations E-Government Survey 2014: E-Government for the future we want. United Nations Department of economic and social affairs. (2014).
20. European Commission, Directorate for Communication of the European Committee of the Regions: From Local to European: Putting citizens at the centre of the EU Agenda. EU Commission, Brussels, Belgium (2019).
21. Toots, M.: Why E-participation systems fail: The case of Estonia's Osale.ee. *Government Information Quarterly*. 36, 546–559 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2019.02.002>.
22. Karlsson, M.: Democratic Legitimacy and Recruitment Strategies in eParticipation Projects. In: Charalabidis, Y. and Koussouris, S. (eds.) *Empowering Open and Collaborative Governance: Technologies and Methods for Online Citizen Engagement in Public Policy Making*. pp. 3–20. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg (2012). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-27219-6_1.

23. Lidén, G.: Qualities of E-Democracy: Examples from Sweden. In: Geißel, B. and Joas, M. (eds.) *Participatory Democratic Innovations in Europe*. pp. 225–248. Verlag Barbara Budrich (2013). <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctvdf0gdc.14>.
24. Cardullo, P., Kitchin, R.: Smart urbanism and smart citizenship: The neoliberal logic of ‘citizen-focused’ smart cities in Europe. *Environment and Planning C: Politics and Space*. 37, 813–830 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1177/0263774X18806508>.
25. Epstein, D., Newhart, M., Vernon, R.: Not by technology alone: The “analog” aspects of online public engagement in policymaking. *Government Information Quarterly*. 31, 337–344 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2014.01.001>.
26. Lember, V.: The increasing role of digital technologies in co-production and co-creation. In: *Co-production and co-creation*. pp. 115–127. Routledge (2018).
27. Norris, D.F.: e-government... not e-governance... not e-democracy not now! not ever? In: *Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on Theory and Practice of Electronic Governance*. pp. 339–346. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA (2010). <https://doi.org/10.1145/1930321.1930391>.
28. Dittrich, Y., Ekelin, A., Elovaara, P., Eriksen, S., Hansson, C.: Making e-government happen everyday co-development of services, citizenship and technology. In: *36th Annual Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences, 2003. Proceedings of the*. p. 12 pp.- (2003). <https://doi.org/10.1109/HICSS.2003.1174328>.
29. van Dijk, J.A.G.M., Peters, O., Ebbers, W.: Explaining the acceptance and use of government Internet services: A multivariate analysis of 2006 survey data in the Netherlands. *Government Information Quarterly*. 25, 379–399 (2008). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2007.09.006>.
30. Delgado, F., Yang, S., Madaio, M., Yang, Q.: The Participatory Turn in AI Design: Theoretical Foundations and the Current State of Practice. In: *Proceedings of the 3rd ACM Conference on Equity and Access in Algorithms, Mechanisms, and Optimization*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3617694.3623261>.
31. Johnson, D.G., Verdicchio, M.: The sociotechnical entanglement of AI and values. *AI & SOCIETY*. 40, 67–76 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-023-01852-5>.
32. Noorman, M., Swierstra, T.: Democratizing AI from a Sociotechnical Perspective. *Minds and Machines*. 33, 563–586 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11023-023-09651-z>.
33. Maas, J., Moreno Inglés, A.: Beyond Participatory AI. *AIES*. 7, 932–942 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1609/aies.v7i1.31693>.
34. Ferraro, C., Demsar, V., Sands, S., Restrepo, M., Campbell, C.: The paradoxes of generative AI-enabled customer service: A guide for managers. *Business Horizons*. 67, 549–559 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bushor.2024.04.013>.
35. Romberg, J., Escher, T.: Making Sense of Citizens’ Input through Artificial Intelligence: A Review of Methods for Computational Text Analysis to Support the Evaluation of Contributions in Public Participation. *Digit. Gov.: Res. Pract.* 5, (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3603254>.
36. Benjamin, J.J., Kinkeldey, C., Müller-Birn, C., Korjakow, T., Herbst, E.-M.: Explanation Strategies as an Empirical-Analytical Lens for Socio-Technical Contextualization of Machine Learning Interpretability. *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* 6, (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3492858>.

37. Prabhakaran, V., Mitchell, M., Gebru, T., Gabriel, I.: A Human Rights-Based Approach to Responsible AI, <https://arxiv.org/abs/2210.02667>, (2022).
38. Amnesty International: Coded Injustice: Surveillance and Discrimination in Denmark's automated welfare state. Amnesty International Ltd, London, UK (2024).
39. Angwin, J., Larson, J., Mattu, S., Kirchner, L.: Machine Bias. In: Martin, K. (ed.) *Ethics of data and analytics*. pp. 254–264. Auerbach Publications (2022).
40. Kalluri, P.: Don't ask if artificial intelligence is good or fair, ask how it shifts power. *Nature*. 583, 169–169 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-020-02003-2>.
41. Costanza-Chock, S.: *Design Justice: Community-Led Practices to Build the Worlds We Need*. The MIT Press (2020). <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/12255.001.0001>.
42. Arnstein, S.R.: A Ladder Of Citizen Participation. *Journal of the American Institute of Planners*. 35, 216–224 (1969). <https://doi.org/10.1080/01944366908977225>.
43. Birhane, A., Prabhu, V.U., Whaley, J.: Auditing Saliency Cropping Algorithms. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Winter Conference on Applications of Computer Vision (WACV)*. pp. 4051–4059 (2022).
44. Sloane, M., Moss, E., Awomolo, O., Forlano, L.: Participation Is not a Design Fix for Machine Learning. In: *Proceedings of the 2nd ACM Conference on Equity and Access in Algorithms, Mechanisms, and Optimization*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3551624.3555285>.
45. Himmelreich, J.: Against “Democratizing AI.” *AI Soc.* 38, 1333–1346 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-021-01357-z>.
46. Gabriel, I.: Toward a Theory of Justice for Artificial Intelligence. *Daedalus*. 151, 218–231 (2022). https://doi.org/10.1162/daed_a_01911.
47. Srnicek, N.: Platform Monopolies and the Political Economy of AI. In: McDonnell, J. (ed.) *Economics for the Many*. pp. 152–163. Verso (2018).
48. Zuboff, S.: The age of surveillance capitalism. In: Longhofer, W. and Winchester, D. (eds.) *Social theory re-wired*. pp. 203–213. Routledge, New York, NY (2023).
49. Pettit, P.: *Republicanism: A theory of freedom and government*. Oxford University Press, Oxford, NY (1997).
50. Bratteteig, T., Wagner, I.: Disentangling power and decision-making in participatory design. In: *Proceedings of the 12th Participatory Design Conference: Research Papers - Volume 1*. pp. 41–50. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1145/2347635.2347642>.
51. Robertson, T., Simonsen, J.: Challenges and Opportunities in Contemporary Participatory Design. *Design Issues*. 28, 3–9 (2012). https://doi.org/10.1162/DESI_a_00157.
52. Cohen, J.: *Justice and the Politics of Difference*. Princeton University Press, Princeton, NJ (1990). <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctvcn4g4q>.
53. Muller, M., Liao, Q.V.: Exploring ai ethics and values through participatory design fictions. *Human Computer Interaction Consortium*. (2017).
54. Donia, J., Shaw, J.A.: Co-design and ethical artificial intelligence for health: An agenda for critical research and practice. *Big Data & Society*. 8, 20539517211065248 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1177/20539517211065248>.
55. Fernández-Martínez, J.L., Lopez-Sanchez, M., Aguilar, J.A.R., Rubio, D.S., Nemegeyi, B.Z.: Co-Designing participatory tools for a New Age: A proposal for combining collective and artificial intelligences. *International Journal of Public Administration in the Digital Age (IJPADA)*. 5, 1–17 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.4018/IJPADA.2018100101>.

56. Kučević, E., von Brackel-Schmidt, C., Lewandowski, T., Leible, S., Memmert, L., Böhmman, T.: The prompt-a-thon: designing a format for value co-creation with generative AI for research and practice. In: Proceedings of the Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS2024) (2024).
57. Duerinckx, A., Veeckman, C., Verstraelen, K., Singh, N., Van Laer, J., Vaes, M., Vandooren, C., Duysburgh, P.: Co-creating Artificial Intelligence: Designing and Enhancing Democratic AI Solutions Through Citizen Science. *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*. (2024). <https://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.732>.
58. Schuler, D., Namioka, A.: *Participatory design: Principles and practices*. CRC press, Boca Raton, FL (1993).
59. Oostveen, A.-M., van den Besselaar, P.: From Small Scale to Large Scale User Participation: A Case Study of Participatory Design in e-Government Systems. In: Proceedings of the Eighth Conference on Participatory Design: Artful Integration: Interweaving Media, Materials and Practices - Volume 1. pp. 173–182. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA (2004). <https://doi.org/10.1145/1011870.1011891>.
60. Anastasiou, L., Elguendouze, S., Efstathiou, I., Mariani, I., Cabrio, E., Villata, S., Karacapilidis, N., Concilio, G., Rizzo, F., Greco, S., Jermini, C., Coppola, C., Apostolopoulou, A., Domalis, G., Tsakalidis, D., De Liddo, A.: ORBIS: An AI-Enabled Architecture for Scaling Online Deliberation. In: Aikins, S. (ed.) *Artificial Intelligence and Government: Examining the Roles and Uses of AI in Enhancing Government Operations*. Springer International, Cham, Switzerland (2026). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-032-12344-2_5.
61. Mariani, I., Anastasiou, L., Elguendouze, S., Rizzo, F., Concilio, G., Cabrio, E., Villata, S., Efstathiou, I., Domalis, G., De Liddo, A.: Enhancing Democratic Deliberations with AI: Insights from the ORBIS Co-Creation Journey. In: Aikins, S. (ed.) *Artificial Intelligence and Government: Examining the Roles and Uses of AI in Enhancing Government Operations*. Springer International, Cham, Switzerland (2026). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-032-12344-2_10.
62. Bellò, B., Downe, J.: We asked, you said, we did: Assessing the drivers and effectiveness of an e-participation practice in Scotland. Presented at the February 15 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781800374362.00009>.
63. De Cindio, F., De Marco, A., Ripamonti, L.A.: Enriching Community Networks by Supporting Deliberation. In: Steinfield, C., Pentland, B.T., Ackerman, M., and Contractor, N. (eds.) *Communities and Technologies 2007*. pp. 395–417. Springer London, London (2007).
64. Wirtz, B.W., Weyerer, J.C., Geyer, C.: Artificial Intelligence and the Public Sector—Applications and Challenges. *International Journal of Public Administration*. 42, 596–615 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1080/01900692.2018.1498103>.
65. Steen, M.: Virtues in Participatory Design: Cooperation, Curiosity, Creativity, Empowerment and Reflexivity. *Science and Engineering Ethics*. 19, 945–962 (2013). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-012-9380-9>.
66. Geels, F.W.: Processes and patterns in transitions and system innovations: Refining the co-evolutionary multi-level perspective. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*. 72, 681–696 (2005). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2004.08.014>.